

Data description for the reproducibility of the results

Manuscript Title

Eringen Number Impact on Magneto-Micropolar Cylinder Flow: FreeFEM++ Simulation with Applications to Ambient and Energy-Driven Cooling Systems

Repository Contents

This draft contains the parameter settings used to generate the numerical results reported in the manuscript. All simulations were performed using the finite element method implemented in FreeFEM++. The source code is available on a reasonable request to the corresponding author at muhammad.sabeel@cust.edu.pk.

Parameter Values Used for Figures

Figures 5 and 6

- $K = 1$
- $\beta = 3$
- $\alpha = 5$
- $100 \leq Re \leq 500$
- $0.005 \leq Er \leq 0.1$

Figure 7

- $K = 1$
- $\alpha = 1$
- $\beta = 1$
- $Re = 100$
- $0.005 \leq Er \leq 0.1$

Figures 8 and 9

- $Re = 100$
- $\alpha = 1$
- $\beta = 0.6$
- $Er = 1.0$
- $0.1 \leq K \leq 1$

Figures 10 and 11

- $Re = 200$
- $Er = 0.01$
- $K = 1$
- $\beta = 1$
- $0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 1.5$

Parameter Values Used for Tables

Table 4

- $K = 1$
- $\alpha = 1$
- $\beta = 0.6$
- $0.001 \leq Er \leq 0.1$
- $50 \leq Re \leq 500$

Table 5

- $\alpha = 1$
- $\beta = 0.6$
- $Er = 0.001$
- $0.1 \leq K \leq 2$
- $50 \leq Re \leq 500$

Table 6

- $Er = 0.01$
- $K = 1$
- $\beta = 0.1$
- $50 \leq Re \leq 500$
- $0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 1.3$

Table 7

- $Er = 0.001$
- $K = 1$
- $\alpha = 0.1$
- $50 \leq Re \leq 500$

Software

All computations were performed using FreeFEM++ finite element software. The source code is available on a reasonable request to the corresponding author at muhammad.sabeel@cust.edu.pk.